

http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

WebPage All (1)

```

1 <!doctype html>
2 <html lang="pt-PT">
3
4 <head>
5 <meta charset="UTF-8">
6 <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, i
7 <link rel="profile" href="https://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
8
9 <title>marketingdigitaltools.com | Marketing Digital
10 <!-- This site is optimized with the Yoast SEO plugin v13.0
11 <meta name="robots" content="max-snippet:-1, max-image-previ
12 <link rel="canonical" href="http://plugin01.marketingdigital
13 <meta property="og:locale" content="pt_PT" />
14 <meta property="og:type" content="website" />
15 <meta property="og:title" content="marketingdigitaltools.com
16 <meta property="og:url" content="http://plugin01.marketingdi
17 <meta property="og:site_name" content="Marketing Digital Too
18 <meta name="twitter:card" content="summary_large_image" />
19 <meta name="twitter:title" content="marketingdigitaltools.co
20 <meta name="twitter:site" content="@mktdigitaltools" />
21 <meta name="twitter:image" content="http://plugin01.marketin
22 <meta name="twitter:creator" content="@mktdigitaltools" />
23 <meta name="google-site-verification" content="sQBj98uIEC3V5
24 <script type="application/ld+json" class="yoast-schema-graph
25 <!-- / Yoast SEO plugin. -->
26 <link rel="dns-prefetch" href="//s.w.org" />
27 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
28 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
29 <script type="text/javascript">
30 window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl":"https://s
31 !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("c
32 </script>
33 <style type="text/css">
34 img.wp-smiley,
35 img.emoji {
36 display: inline !important;
37 border: none !important;
38 box-shadow: none !important;
39 height: 1em !important;
40 width: 1em !important;
41 margin: 0 .07em !important;
42 vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
43 background: none !important;
44 padding: 0 !important;
45 }
46 </style>
47 <link rel="stylesheet" id="wp-block-library-css" href="ht
48 <link rel="stylesheet" id="wc-block-style-css" href="http://g
49 <link rel="stylesheet" id="dashicons-css" href="http://plugi
50 <link rel="stylesheet" id="everest-forms-general-css" href="ht
51 <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-layout-css" href="http
52 <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-small-screen-css" href=
53 <link rel="stylesheet" id="woocommerce-general-css" href="htt
54 <style id="woocommerce-inline-inline-css" type="text/css">
55 .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
56 </style>
57 <link rel="stylesheet" id="font-awesome-css" href="http://plu
58 <link rel="stylesheet" id="zakra-style-css" href="http://plug
59 <style id="zakra-style-inline-css" type="text/css">
60 @media (min-width: 1200px) { .tg-container{max-width: 1200px;}
61 .tg-primary-menu > div ul li a{font-family: -apple-system, bli
62 </style>
63 <link rel="stylesheet" id="zakra-woocommerce-style-css" href=
64 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-icons-css" href="http://
65 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-animations-css" href="ht
66 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-frontend-css" href="http
67 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-global-css" href="http://
68 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-post-24-css" href="http:
69 <link rel="stylesheet" id="google-fonts-1-css" href="https://
70 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-icons-shared-0-css" href
71 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-icons-fa-solid-css" href
72 <link rel="stylesheet" id="elementor-icons-fa-brands-css" href
73 <script type="text/javascript" src="http://plugin01.marketing
74 <script type="text/javascript" src="http://plugin01.marketing
75 <link rel="https://api.w.org/" href="http://plugin01.marketing
76 <link rel="EditURI" type="application/rsd+xml" title="RSD" href
77 <link rel="wlwmanifest" type="application/wlwmanifest+xml" href
78 <meta name="generator" content="WordPress 5.3.3" />
79 <meta name="generator" content="Everest Forms 1.5.10" />
80 <meta name="generator" content="WooCommerce 3.9.1" />
81 <link rel="shortlink" href="http://plugin01.marketingdigitalto
82 <link rel="alternate" type="application/json+oembed" href="htt
83 <link rel="alternate" type="text/xml+oembed" href="http://plug
84 <noscript><style>.woocommerce-product-gallery{ opacity: 1
85 <style type="text/css">
86 .site-title,
87 .site-description {
88 position: absolute;
89 clip: rect(1px, 1px, 1px, 1px);
90 }
91 </style>
92 <link rel="icon" href="http://plugin01.marketingdigit
93 <link rel="icon" href="http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.c
94 <link rel="apple-touch-icon-precomposed" href="http://plugin0
95 <meta name="msapplication-TileImage" content="http://plugin01
96 <style type="text/css" id="wp-custom-css">

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WebPage		0 ERROS 0 AVISOS	
ID: http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/#webpage			
@type	WebPage		
@id	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/#webpage		
url	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/		
inLanguage	pt-PT		
name	marketingdigitaltools.com Marketing Digital Tools		
datePublished	2019-02-02T15:11:19+00:00		
dateModified	2020-02-04T12:22:30+00:00		
isPartOf			
@type	WebSite		
@id	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/#website		
url	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/		
name	Marketing Digital Tools		
description	Agência de Marketing Digital Ecommerce		
publisher			
@type	Organization		
@id	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/#organization		
name	Marketing Digital Tools		
url	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/		
sameAs	https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/		
sameAs	https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools/		
sameAs	https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/		
sameAs	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFw/featured		
sameAs	https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools		
logo			
@type	ImageObject		
@id	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/#logo		
url	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-Marketing-Digital-Tools-com-Slogan.png		
width	463		
height	330		
caption	Marketing Digital Tools		
image			
@type	ImageObject		
@id	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/#logo		
url	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-Marketing-Digital-Tools-com-Slogan.png		
width	463		
height	330		
caption	Marketing Digital Tools		
potentialAction			
@type	SearchAction		
target			
@type	EntryPoint		
urlTemplate	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/?s={search_term_string}		
query-input			
@type	PropertyValueSpecification		
valueRequired	http://schema.org/True		
valueName	search_term_string		
about			
@type	Organization		
@id	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/#organization		
name	Marketing Digital Tools		
url	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/		
sameAs	https://www.facebook.com/marketingdigitaltools/		
sameAs	https://www.instagram.com/marketingdigitaltools/		
sameAs	https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/		
sameAs	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i5zFw/featured		
sameAs	https://twitter.com/mktdigitaltools		
logo			
@type	ImageObject		
@id	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/#logo		
url	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Logo-Marketing-Digital-Tools-com-Slogan.png		
width	463		
height	330		
caption	Marketing Digital Tools		
primaryImageOfPage			
@type	ImageObject		
@id	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/#primaryimage		
url	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/PLANO-MKT-VISIBILIDADE.png		
width	1680		
height	1680		
caption	Plano Visibilidade Marketing Digital Tools		